

CRIMINOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD

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Crime Data in India: Myths, Misreporting, and Misinterpretations

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Introduction

Benjamin Disraeli famously said, “There are three types of lies – lies, damn lies, and statistics.” This quote, often attributed to Mark Twain as well, underscores the deceptive power of statistics. The remark highlights how statistical data, despite its appearance of objectivity, can be manipulated to mislead and distort the truth. It serves as a cautionary reminder that numbers, when selectively presented or interpreted, can convey a false narrative, thus requiring a critical approach to understanding and evaluating statistical claims.

In India, one of the most glaring examples of this deception lies in the portrayal of crime statistics. Official crime data often fails to reflect the true extent of criminal activity due to underreporting, inconsistent data collection methods, and political pressures to present a more favorable image of public safety. This discrepancy between reported and actual crime rates can create a false sense of security and hinder effective policy-making.

The Fallacy of Data vis-à-vis Reporting Behavior

The “Crime in India – 2021” report, published by the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) under the Ministry of Home Affairs, compiles crime data from every state’s crime records bureau. While this compilation is extensive, the methodology and credibility of state crime records raise significant issues. Following the report’s publication, media outlets like the Indian Express highlighted alarming statistics, such as a 15.3% increase in crimes against women. Delhi, Mumbai, and Bangalore were labeled the most unsafe cities for women, overshadowing states known for high crime rates like Uttar Pradesh and Bihar. This discrepancy points to the fallacy of the data. The primary issue with these statistics is the poor reporting behavior in India. Higher crime statistics often reflect better reporting rather than higher actual crime rates. Cities like Lucknow and Patna may not appear in top crime lists due to underreporting, not a lack of crime. This leads to a distorted perception of safety in different regions.

Despite the data’s questionable authenticity, it is widely accepted and propagated by national media as accurate. This perpetuates misinformation among the public. For example, the NCRB data shows higher suicide rates in southern states like Kerala and Tamil Nadu compared to northern states like Uttar Pradesh and Bihar. This does not mean suicides are less frequent in the north; rather, they are underreported. In states like Haryana, societal structures like Khap Panchayats can prevent accurate reporting of suicides and honor killings, further skewing the data.

Despite being an official document, the NCRB report includes disclaimers about the data’s authenticity and limitations. The “Principal Offence Rule,” which only counts the most serious crime in multiple-offence cases, can lead to underreporting of less severe crimes.

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The NCRB's disclaimer admits they only compile existing data without verifying its accuracy, undermining the report's credibility. It is ironic that the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), which operates under the Ministry of Home Affairs, has acknowledged the unreliability of its own crime statistics, stating that they are not responsible for their accuracy. While this admission might seem acceptable in isolation, the problem arises when these statistics are disseminated by the media as credible. Media outlets, including reputable ones like The Hindu and Indian Express, often report these statistics uncritically, leading to public misinformation. Educated audiences, who rely on these sources, form opinions based on potentially inaccurate data. The media's failure to critically analyze or explain the limitations of these statistics is concerning.

Issues with Crime Data: My Personal Experiences with the Police and Prisons

Long back, during a Crime Mapping Study in a South Indian city, I collected data from the Crime Records Bureau and created crime maps highlighting hotspots—areas with higher crime rates. When a Deputy Commissioner saw the map, he told me it was incorrect. I explained that the map was based on their data, but he admitted that they had spread crime data across different areas to make it appear more balanced. This experience deterred me from creating crime maps with such data. Hopefully, crime data collection and reporting have improved since then.

Additionally, during a visit to a prominent jail in a Western Indian city, I discovered over 700 inmates labeled as rape offenders. Upon investigation, I found that many of these inmates were young men aged 18-21 in consensual relationships with girls under 18. The law does not consider these relationships consensual due to the Indian Majority Act of 1875, which sets the age of majority at 18. This legal technicality results in young people being imprisoned. Meanwhile, the Factories Act of 1948 allows children under 14 to work in non-hazardous industries, highlighting the inconsistencies in defining the age of consent. High Courts and the Chief Justice of India have urged the government to lower the age of consent from 18 to 16, but the government has no plans to do so. This legal discrepancy has led to many young people being unjustly imprisoned.

Comparing India and the United States in Crime Data Analysis

The USA's Bureau of Justice Statistics (BJS) emphasizes credible and objective crime analysis, conducting large-scale victimization surveys annually. This approach contrasts sharply with the NCRB's reliance on secondary data. The BJS's independence from external influence and rigorous data collection and verification processes ensure more accurate crime statistics.

Unlike the NCRB's method of data collection, which relies solely on secondary data from the respective State Crime Records Bureaus (SCRBs), the Bureau of Justice Statistics (BJS) conducts an extensive annual survey known as the "National Crime Victimization Survey" (NCVS). This survey serves as the primary source of information on criminal victimization in the United States. Each year, researchers, scholars, and enumerators conduct individual interviews with over 240,000 people from around 150,000 households to compile the report.

India lacks a comprehensive crime victimization survey like the BJS's National Crime Victimization Survey. Reliance on secondary data prevents a deep understanding of crime trends. Additionally, past victimization surveys by Indian universities have suffered from biases, further questioning the reliability of such data. Rigorous guidelines and quality control are essential to ensure accurate data collection.

Conclusion

The NCRB report's list of officers involved in its creation reveals a lack of criminologists and statisticians in key roles. To improve the credibility of crime statistics, the NCRB should be headed by a criminologist or social scientist with significant experience in the management of crime data and analysis. A dedicated team of criminologists, sociologists, data scientists, and statisticians should handle crime analysis independently, free from external influence. Implementing crime victimization surveys and establishing Crime Analysis Units (CAUs) in each police department, as practiced in the USA, would significantly enhance the accuracy of crime data. Further, numerous factors, including literacy rates, caste, religion, economic background, gender, and political power, influence crime reporting behavior and data accuracy. Addressing these issues requires a multifaceted approach involving independent research, rigorous data collection, and critical analysis to ensure reliable crime statistics in India.

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